

Analysis of Changes to Tobyhanna Army Depot Maintenance Cycle

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Abstract— As part of a year-long study for the Department of Systems Engineering at West Point, our Capstone project seeks to provide Tobyhanna Army Depot with a decision support tool that will quantify how changes in Depot Maintenance programs, to include the exploration of reset and recap maintenance for the AN/TPQ 37 Firefinder will affect the readiness, time, cost, reliability, and support costs of the Firefinder.

The AN/TPQ 37 Firefinder is a mobile radar system that provides detection of incoming artillery and rocket fire and tracks its movement in order to provide a location for counter-battery fire. This study is important because it incorporates an interdisciplinary approach to solving a complex problem using elements of industrial engineering, systems thinking, as well as modeling in producing a decision support tool that will allow Tobyhanna to make changes to their resources and service times in order to analyze these effects on turnaround times.

The problem will be solved in two phases. The first phase will be to model the current operations at Tobyhanna Army Depot by using the AnyLogic simulation tool. This will be done by analyzing maintenance data and using the AnyLogic simulation tool in order to model their current system turnaround of 180 days. Once this is complete and approved by Tobyhanna Army Depot, inputs in AnyLogic will be altered in order to show how these changes will impact service turnaround times.

So far, we have achieved an average turnaround time of 6 months with our current model. We have also succeeded in providing a decision support tool to Tobyhanna Army Depot that will allow them to alter their resource and labor constraints in order to accurately model what its impact on turnaround time will be.

I. INTRODUCTION

The AN/TPQ-37 Firefinder is a mobile radar system that works in conjunction with Field Artillery units in order to provide a tracking system to assist counter batteries to engage incoming enemy rockets and mortars. The point of origin of enemy fire can be detected using the AN/TP-37, which has proved important in assisting the International Security Assistance Force in combating insurgents in Afghanistan.

The purpose of this project is to assist Tobyhanna Army Depot in providing a decision support tool that is able to quantify changes in Depot Maintenance programs, to include

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the exploration of reset and recap maintenance for the Q37 Firefinder and determine how it will affect the readiness, time, cost, and reliability of the Q37 no later than May 2013. This process will be modeled using “AnyLogic Professional” in order to adequately display all components of the maintenance as it goes through the full analytical and repair process at Tobyhanna. The AN/TPQ-37 has many variant models, each with unique specifications. As a result, the maintenance of one model may be very different when compared to another model. Currently, Tobyhanna is able to reach a turnaround time of 6 months when a Firefinder is brought in for maintenance, which is a vast improvement from the previous turnaround time of one year.

II. TOBYHANNA ARMY DEPOT

Tobyhanna Army Depot was established in February 1, 1953 as a signal depot. Currently, it serves as a facility that repairs, upgrades, and integrates C4ISR (command, control, computer, communications, intelligence, surveillance, reconnaissance) systems for all branches of the United States military. One of their key systems that they are responsible for is the AN/TPQ-37 Firefinder Radar System.

The Firefinder works by detecting an incoming artillery round by performing a 90-degree sector scan. As it tracks the incoming round, it pinpoints the origin of which it was fired from, allowing counter battery fire to eliminate further aggression. This system has been deployed to help fight against mortar and rocket attacks from insurgents in Afghanistan. Through normal wear and tear, the Firefinder comes back to Tobyhanna for servicing. There are two types of maintenance operations: scheduled and condition-based maintenance. Tobyhanna can only process four systems at one time due to spacing constraints. From this, they have tasked us to determine if something can be done to improve turnaround time by not yielding on performance or cost.

Fig.1. AN/TPQ-37 Firefinder Radar System

III. STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS

Tobyhanna Army Depot has gained their reputation by providing their clients with the highest quality of maintenance performed in the quickest amount of time possible.

Fig. 2. Functional Hierarchy of Tobyhanna Army Depot

They accomplish this by seeking to minimize wait-time for parts and minimizing labor wait-time. These factors help Tobyhanna achieve an optimal and turnaround time without jeopardizing the quality of their finished systems.

V. OBJECTIVES

The following are the objectives of our capstone project:

Analyze the current maintenance process at Tobyhanna with regards to the AN/TPQ-37 Firefinder in order to reach their repair turnaround time of 6 months.

- This will be done by utilizing historic data that shows four AN/TPQ-37 Firefinder systems within the maintenance cycle.
- Current labor and resources usage data.

Analyze the effect of variables that can be adjusted within the AnyLogic simulation tool that may reduce the turnaround time of Tobyhanna Army Depot.

- Labor
- Proximity of Resources
- Wait-times of Ordered Parts

VI. DESIRED ENDSTATE

Provide Tobyhanna Army Depot with a decision support tool that allows them to manually input their resources and labor so that they may have an accurate estimation of its effects on turnaround time.

VII. MAINTENANCE CYCLE

The maintenance process at the Tobyhanna Depot consists of a variety of stages.

Fig. 3. Process flow layout of the AN-TPQ 37 Firefinder at Tobyhanna Army Depot.

Initially, the Firefinder spends one week in the Evaluation and Inspection phase. Next, it will take 2 weeks to thoroughly disassemble and clean each component of the Firefinder. Once this phase is complete, 1 week will be devoted to structural repair of the system before it is given 2 weeks for reassembly. At this point, the antenna is tested to ensure proper function and serviceability. A Musson test is performed which essentially subjects the system to a series of vibrations and shocks to replicate the terrain in which it will most likely be deployed to. An electrical test is performed for three weeks which tests the electrical components of the system. For three days, a system burn-in is performed followed by re-paint. A one week period is set aside for final testing before it is shipped back to its owners.

VIII. ASSUMPTIONS

Several assumptions were made in order to facilitate the execution of the modeling portion of our project:

- Neglect transport times between service stations
- No set limit on AN/TPQ 37 Firefinder progressing through the maintenance cycle at any given time.

IX. ANYLOGIC MODELING METHODOLOGY

The first step in utilizing the AnyLogic simulation tool was to create a realistic flow diagram of the AN/TQP 37 Firefinder maintenance floor at Tobyhanna Army Depot.

Fig. 4. AnyLogic Process Flow

Fig. 5. 2D Process flow layout of the AN/TPQ-37 Firefinder maintenance cycle on AnyLogic

From this two-dimensional model, we were able to convert it into a three-dimensional one that would be more visibly understood by key personnel at Tobyhanna.

Fig. 6. 3D Process flow layout of the AN-TPQ 37 Firefinder maintenance cycle on AnyLogic.

At each maintenance station, a service was added to the simulation program, which was then connected to subsequent services using a queue and conveyor belt. The times through the queue and conveyor belt were set at zero in order to satisfy the program functionality. After analyzing the historic data provided to us by Tobyhanna, a triangular distribution was fitted with an upper bound, mean, and lower bound. This gave us the average amount of time an AN/TPQ-37 completes a maintenance cycle. Resources were added to each station on AnyLogic that matched the provided data to accurately model the time required to complete each task at the service stations. Figure 5 below shows the median service breakdown on AnyLogic:

Fig. 7. Median service breakdown

TABLE 1: SERVICE STATION ANALYSIS

Service Station	Lower Bound (Days)	Median (Days)	Upper Bound (Days)
Disassembly	15.5	19.5	24.5
Repair	18	28	35
CompTest	10	13	16
AntScan	14	19	23
Reassembly	4	6	8
Munson Test	9	11	14
Electric Test	37	53	60
Burn In	11	14	18
Tower	20	27	31
Paint	14	19	23
Finalize	10	13	17
Sum		222.5	

The finished model shows an AN/TPQ-37 as a package that splits into component parts upon arrival. These parts are sent to their respective service stations while Java was used to record the average time in system of each system. The arrival rate of the model was set at two Firefinder systems per month, as per the request of our stakeholders. Finally, we created a user input section within the model that allows Tobyhanna to select the amount of worker or resources they want at each station in order to view its impact on turnaround times.

X. SIGNIFICANCE OF WORK

In today's uncertain economic climate, resource efficiency is key in lowering costs to maximize net profits. By creating a model that simulates and analyzes changes made in resource and labor utilization, Tobyhanna will be able to quantify changes made to their maintenance cycle. We believe that our capstone work possesses significance because of the way in which it will help Tobyhanna Army Depot become more prepared for adapting to changes that involve labor and resources. The sequestration that is in effect for the Department of Defense also places constraints on companies like Tobyhanna to find ways to adjust to less resources. Tobyhanna will be able to use our tool to allow them to accurately estimate what the impact of labor and resource changes will have on their turnaround time.

XI. FUTURE WORK

Future work on this project will involve being able to refine our input tool to provide Tobyhanna with better analysis on changes to resources. Currently, we are seeing turn-around times increase with increased resources, which may mean that further refinement is needed to show a more likely result of decreased times. We would also like to incorporate stockage levels in order to see what the optimal balance will be with regards to the availability of maintenance parts to further reduce turnaround time.

XII. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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